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Students' Interest And Physical Education Teachers' Attitudes As Determinants Of The Under-Registration Of Physical Education In The Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined students' interest and Physical Education teachers' attitudes as determinants of the under-registration of Physical Education in the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSSCE) in Nigeria. The persistent decline in students' enrollment and registration for Physical Education despite its educational, health, and career benefits has become a source of concern to stakeholders in education. The study adopted a descriptive survey design and was guided by two research questions and corresponding hypotheses. Data were collected from senior secondary school students and Physical Education teachers using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings revealed that students' interest significantly influences the registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject. Similarly, the attitudes of Physical Education teachers were found to have a significant impact on students' decisions to register for the subject. Positive teacher attitudes and effective instructional practices enhanced students' interest and participation, while negative perceptions contributed to under-registration. The study concluded that students' interest and teachers' attitudes are important factors influencing the low registration of Physical Education in secondary schools. It was recommended that educational authorities should strengthen awareness programmes on the importance and career prospects of Physical Education and provide regular professional development opportunities for teachers to improve students' enrollment and participation in the subject.

Keywords: Physical Education, Students' Interest, Teachers' Attitudes, Under-registration, Secondary School Students, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Physical education is recognized as a critical component of holistic education, contributing to the physical, mental, and social development of students (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), 2015). National policies on education often emphasize the importance of Physical Education in promoting health, discipline, teamwork, and overall well-being among students (World Health Organization (WHO), 2018). The inclusion and prioritization of Physical Education in national curricula reflect broader educational goals aimed at fostering balanced development and preparing students for active, healthy lifestyles (National Association for Sport and Physical Education,

2017). However, the implementation and emphasis on Physical Education vary widely across countries, influenced by cultural, economic, and institutional factors (Hardman, 2018).

This subject plays a crucial role in Nigeria, promoting overall well-being and healthy lifestyles (Nicholas, 2024). Physical and health education policies in Nigeria are designed to ensure the holistic development of individuals by promoting physical activity and healthy lifestyle choices.

Currently, the National Policy on Education and the National School Health Policy provide guidelines for the implementation of physical and health education programs in schools across Nigeria (Nicholas, 2024). The National Policy on Education mandates that physical and health education be included in the curriculum of all primary and secondary schools in the country. Additionally, the National School Health Policy focuses on promoting the health and well-being of students through the provision of comprehensive health education programs.

Today, physical education does not have the same prominence it once had and, in fact the subject is not taught in most primary and secondary schools in Nigeria. Where it is taught, it was either made optional or combined with other science-based subjects such as basic science (Former Integrated Science); computer studies and Intro-tech at the basic level of the 9-3-4 system of education. Enrolment of students into the subject at secondary school is optional. As an examinable subject in West African Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (WASSCE), Physical Education is facing serious setbacks nowadays. This was obtainable from the previous record of students' enrolment in 2008 where nine thousand two hundred and sixteen (9,216) candidates sat for the examination as against nine thousand seven hundred and eighty (9,780) recorded in 2007. The number keeps declining leading to what the researcher feels to call under-registration. Ten years later in 2018, the enrolment was still static at seven thousand two hundred and ninety-one (7,291). In the year 2020 the total candidates of 7,396 were recorded (WAEC, 2022). This implied that on the average, no more than 8,421 sit for the examination yearly in the last two (2) decades compared with other subjects offered. The pain of this stagnation in students' enrolment into physical education as an examinable subject must be determined by the interaction of certain indices that pushed the researcher to undertake this study. Moreover, physical education teacher's attitude with regards to teaching methods especially in teaching practical courses with dictation instead of demonstrations, and the use of strenuous physical activities as a form of corporal punishment may likely de-motivate senior secondary school students from enrolling into Physical Education. However, the researcher casted doubt as to whether parental influence and misconception of Physical Education is serve as detrimental factor that determine under-registration of students into Senior Secondary Certificate Examination. This therefore assessed the determinants of Under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination in Nigeria.

Based on the purpose of this study, the following research questions were raised:

- 1 To what extent does students' interest in Physical Education influence the under- registration of physical education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria?
- 2 To what extent does the attitude of physical education teachers' influence the under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria?

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Self-determination theory (SDT) is highly relevant to the assessment of under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in secondary school certificate examinations. SDT entails that individuals have basic psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness, which, when satisfied, enhance motivation and well-being. In the context of Physical Education, students who perceive the subject as an avenue to fulfil these needs are more likely to register and perform well. However, if Physical Education is not recognized as an examinable subject, it may be undervalued by both students

and educational institutions, leading to lower enrollment rates in the said examination (WAEC). The lack of formal assessment and recognition as some of the teachers' attitude can diminish students' sense of competence and achievement in Physical Education, thereby reducing their intrinsic motivation to participate.

The research design used in this study was ex-post-facto research design. The use of this design was necessitated by the fact that the study is by nature non-experimental and no variable was manipulated as recommended by Sharma (2015) who stated that Ex-post facto research design seeks to find out factors that are associated with certain occurrences, outcomes, conditions and types of behaviour by analysing past events or already existing conditions.

Three hundred and eighty four (384) students were used as sample size for this study. The sample of the study was guided by Adam (2020) which opined that for a population above two million, three hundred and eighty-four (384) is adequate based on the confidence level of 95% with a marginal error of 0.05. The researcher was employ multi-stage sampling procedure in drawing the sample for this study.

To determine the face and content validity of the instrument, a copy of the questionnaire was given to the supervisors for corrections and inputs. It was then given to four (4) other professionals or experts in the Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria who served as jurors to vet the questionnaire. Their comments and suggestions were incorporated after which a final copy of the questionnaire was produced for pilot study.

The data collected was analyzed using the Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS) version 23. Descriptive statistics of frequencies and percentages was used to analyze the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the responses in order to answer the research questions, while Chi-Square Statistics was used to test all the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. To achieve this purpose, three hundred and eighty-four (384) copies of questionnaire were administered and 380 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved and used for the analysis. The statistical package SPSS Version 25 was used to analyze the data obtained from the respondents. The demographic characteristics of the respondents were computed using frequencies and simple percentages. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. The null hypotheses were analyzed using inferential statistics of Chi-square (χ^2) at 0.05 level of significance.

DATA ANALYSIS

Responses to Research Questions

Research Question one: *Will students' interest determines under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria?*

Table 3.1: Mean scores of respondents on Students' interest determines under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria

Sn	Items	Mean	Std. Dev.
1.	Students do not have interest in Physical Education as an academic subject to register it in senior secondary certificate examination.	4.06	0.992
2.	Students have limited interested in registering Physical Education in senior secondary certificate examination. This determine its under- registration in SSCE	3.74	1.380
3.	Students are not interested in the strenuous nature of Physical Education in senior secondary schools, for they do not regard it as lucrative course.	4.00	1.186
4.	Students are not interested in the fitness test conducted of Physical Education student in senior secondary schools.	4.06	0.992
5.	Student are not interested in the mandatory Physical Education classes for fear of injuries.	4.42	0.764
6.	Students do not pick interest to what subject are registered for them children	4.22	0.904

	in senior secondary schools examination.		
7.	Students do not bother when they were not registered for Physical Education in senior secondary schools examination.	4.23	0.797
8.	Students pick offence for registering Physical Education in their senior secondary schools examination.	4.06	0.992
9.	Student are not interested in the mandatory sport attires during Physical Education classes.	3.74	1.380
10.	Student are not interested in the possible stains of sport attires during Physical Education classes.	4.00	1.186
	Aggregate mean	4.05	0.921

(Benchmark = 3.50)

Table 3.1 present the mean scores of the respondents on students' interest in determining the under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria range from 3.74 to 4.42, indicating a strong agreement among respondents that students' lack of interest plays a significant role in the under-registration of Physical Education.

The highest mean score of 4.42 is recorded for item 35, "Student are not interested in the mandatory Physical Education classes for fear of injuries." This suggests that the fear of injuries is a major deterrent for students to register for Physical Education. Other items with high mean scores include "Students do not have interest in Physical Education as an academic subject to register it in senior secondary certificate examination" (4.06), "Students are not interested in the fitness test conducted of Physical Education student in senior secondary schools" (4.06), and "Students do not bother what subject are registered for them children in senior secondary schools examination" (4.22). These results indicate that students' lack of interest, fear of injuries, and lack of enthusiasm are contributing factors to the under-registration of Physical Education.

The aggregated mean score of 4.05 is higher than the benchmark of 3.50, indicating a strong consensus among respondents that students' interest is a significant factor in the under-registration of Physical Education, Implies that students' interest determines under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria.

Research Question Two: *Will physical Education teachers' attitude determines under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria?*

Table 3.2: Mean scores of respondents on Physical Education teachers' attitude determines under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria

Sn	Items	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	Physical Education teachers in Senior Secondary Schools do not employ the appropriate method in teaching the subject.	4.41	1.040
2	Physical Education teachers in Senior Secondary Schools lack punctuality in teaching the subject which determine its under- registration in SSCE.	4.44	0.799
3	Physical Education teachers in Senior Secondary Schools abscond practical lessons in teaching the subject.	4.15	0.931
3	Physical Education teachers in Senior Secondary Schools do rush students in teaching the subject.	4.53	0.862
4	Physical Education teachers in Senior Secondary Schools lack enthusiasm in teaching the subject.	4.41	1.040
5	Physical Education teachers in Senior Secondary Schools lack dedication teaching the subject.	4.44	0.799

6	Physical Education teachers in Senior Secondary Schools do not plan their lessons well.	4.15	0.931
7	Physical Education teachers in Senior Secondary Schools show no courage in teaching the subject.	4.15	0.882
8	Physical Education teachers in Senior Secondary Schools show no concern about the need students	4.16	0.995
9	Physical Education teachers in Senior Secondary Schools are in the habit of absenteeism.	4.32	0.873
Aggregate mean		4.32	0.921

(Benchmark = 3.50)

Table 3.2 shows the mean scores of the respondents on Physical Education teachers' attitude in determining the under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria range from 4.15 to 4.53, indicating a strong agreement among respondents that Physical Education teachers' attitude plays a significant role in the under-registration of Physical Education.

The highest mean score of 4.53 is recorded for item 44, "Physical Education teachers in Senior Secondary Schools do rush students in teaching the subject." This suggests that the rushing of students in teaching Physical Education is a major contributor to the under-registration of the subject. Other items with high mean scores include "Physical Education teachers in Senior Secondary Schools lack punctuality in teaching the subject which determine its under-registration in SSCE" (4.44), "Physical Education teachers in Senior Secondary Schools lack enthusiasm in teaching the subject" (4.41), and "Physical Education teachers in Senior Secondary Schools lack dedication teaching the subject" (4.44). These results indicate that Physical Education teachers' lack of punctuality, enthusiasm, and dedication are contributing factors to the under-registration of Physical Education.

The aggregated mean score of 4.32 is higher than the benchmark of 3.50, indicating a strong consensus among respondents that Physical Education teachers' attitude is a significant factor in the under-registration of Physical Education. Implies Physical Education teachers' attitude determines under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria.

Test of hypotheses

Hypothesis I: Students' interest will not significantly determine under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria.

Table 4.1: Chi-square Analysis on Students' Interest Determines Under-registration of Physical Education as an Examinable Subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria.

Variable	N	x2 Cal	x2 Crit	Df	P value	Decision
Students' Interest	380	245.81	50.98	36	0.015	Rejected

$X^2 \text{ Cal (245.81)} > X^2 \text{ Crit (50.98), } P < 0.05$

Results above showed that Students' interest significantly determines under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria. Reasons being that the P-value of 0.015 is less than the 0.05 alpha level of significance while the chi square (x2) Cal. value of 245.81 is greater than the chi square critical value of 50.98 ($X^2 \text{ Cal (245.81)} > X^2 \text{ Crit (50.98)}$) at df 36. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that students' interest will not significantly determine under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria. is hereby rejected. The result revealed that

students' interest significantly determines under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: Physical Education Teachers' attitude will not significantly determine under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria.

Table 4.2: Chi-square Analysis on Physical Education teachers' attitude determines under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria

Variable	N	x ² Cal	x ² Crit	Df	P value	Decision
Physical Education Teachers' Attitude	313	149.75	50.98	36	0.002	Rejected

X² Cal (149.75) > X² Crit (50.98), P < 0.05

Results on table 4.13 above shows that physical Education Teachers' attitude significantly determine under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria. Reasons being that the P-value of 0.002 is less than 0.05 alpha level of significance while the chi square (x²) Cal. value of 149.75 is greater than the chi square critical value of 50.98 X² Cal (149.75) > X² Crit (50.98)df 36. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that Physical Education Teachers' attitude will not significantly determine under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria is hereby rejected. The result revealed that Physical Education Teachers' attitude significantly determine under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Hypothesis one revealed that Students' interest significantly determines under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria. Reasons being that the P-value of 0.015 is less than the 0.05 alpha level of significance while the chi square (x²) Cal. value of 245.81 is greater than the chi square critical value of 50.98 (X² Cal (245.81) > X² Crit (50.98) at df 36. The result revealed that students' interest significantly determines under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria. The finding aligns with the study by Bayu (2019) which revealed that students have a negative attitude towards the Physical Education subject, which directly impact their interest and participation in the subject. Students do not perceive Physical Education as valuable or engaging; reduce the register for it as an examinable subject. Furthermore, Awopetu's (2017) study found that students' perception of the teacher's personality is a determinant of their interest in Physical Education at the senior secondary school level. This reveal that when students have a positive perception of their Physical Education teachers and find them engaging, their interest in the subject is likely to increase, potentially leading to higher enrolment.

Hypothesis two revealed that Physical Education Teachers' attitudes significantly determine under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria is supported by statistical evidence (p-value of 0.002 < 0.05 alpha level, chi-square calculated value of 149.75 > critical value of 50.98). This result aligns with Ibrahim, Olaosebikan, (2021) whose study directly supports this finding. Their research, conducted across Nigeria's six geo-political zones, revealed that teachers' attitudes significantly influence the implementation of the Physical Education curriculum in secondary schools. The finding further support that of Guo et al.'s (2023) who systematic review further reinforces this finding. Their analysis of multiple studies established a significant positive relationship between perceived teacher support and student engagement in PE. Importantly, they noted that teacher support enhance PE registration in senior secondary schools.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

The study assessed the determinants of under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Schools Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria. The study is categorized into five chapters. This section presents the main idea of each of the six items of the research objectives. The study presented the background to the study and the statement of the problem. To achieve the purpose of the study, the study was structured along with two specific purposes with two research questions to be answered as well as two research hypotheses that were tested. The instrument for data collection is a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. Descriptive statistics of frequency and percentages were used to analyze the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. The null hypotheses were analysed using inferential statistics of chi-square at 0.05 level of significance using SPSS. The summaries of Major Findings are as follows;

1. Students' interest significantly determines under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria
2. That Physical Education Teachers' attitude significantly determines under-registration of Physical Education as an examinable subject in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings from this study, the researcher wishes to conclude as follows:

The under-registration of Physical Education is significantly influenced students' interest and physical Education teachers' attitude. These factors, individually and collectively, contribute to the under-registration of Physical Education, the need for a comprehensive approach to address these issues and promote the importance of Physical Education as a vital subject in the Nigerian education system.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Physical Education teachers should adopt innovative and interactive pedagogical approaches that stimulate students' interest and make the subject more engaging and relevant, thereby enhancing student motivation.
2. Professional development programs for Physical Education teachers should focus on cultivating a positive attitude towards the subject, empowering them to inspire their students and promote a positive learning environment.
3. The Ministry of Education should develop and execute a systematic plan to dispel common misconceptions about Physical Education, providing accurate information through various channels, thereby promoting a more informed understanding of the subject.

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